

Predictive Modelling of Antimicrobial Therapy Response and Bacterial Dynamics Using Survival Analytics and Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial therapy plays a critical role in controlling bacterial infections and improving patient outcomes. However, treatment success is often complicated by bacterial persistence, delayed clearance, and recurrence, which are not adequately captured by conventional endpoint-based evaluations. Existing studies have largely focused on antimicrobial resistance, treatment outcomes, or predictive modelling independently, with limited attention to the temporal dynamics of bacterial response throughout treatment. This study proposes an integrated modelling of antimicrobial therapy response and bacterial dynamics using hybrid survival and Machine Learning approaches. A longitudinal dataset comprising 220 observations from 50 patients undergoing antimicrobial treatment was analysed. Generalised Estimating Equations (GEE) were employed to evaluate population-averaged treatment effects, while Kaplan-Meier Estimation (KME) and Cox proportional hazards (CPH) regression were used to investigate time-to-bacterial clearance. Random Survival Forest (RSF) and Gradient Boosted Survival Models (GBM) were further developed to assess predictive performance and risk stratification. In addition, patient-state transition analysis was used to characterise bacterial persistence, clearance, and recurrence patterns. The results showed that bacterial persistence was the predominant treatment trajectory, accounting for more than half of the observed patient responses. Whereas sustained clearance occurred in a smaller proportion of patients. Longitudinal analysis revealed a progressive decline in bacterial positivity over time. Survival analysis indicated that active antimicrobial therapies were associated with approximately 2- to 3-fold higher bacterial clearance rates compared with placebo. Among the predictive models evaluated, the CPH model achieved the highest discrimination performance ($C\text{-index} = 0.587$), outperforming RSF (0.500) and GBM (0.393).

Keywords: Antimicrobial Therapy, Bacterial Dynamics, Drug Discovery, Survival Analysis, Machine Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial therapy remains one of the most important advances in modern medicine. It significant to reducing the burden of bacterial infections and contributing to global health improvements (Brüssow, 2024). Hence, the discovery and development of antibiotics have transformed the management of infectious diseases. Effective treatment of conditions once associated with high morbidity and mortality are now easily addressed. Moreso, advances in antimicrobial discovery have expanded the range of available treatment options and improved clinical outcomes across diverse healthcare settings. These include natural product screening, synthetic drug development, molecular target identification, and genomics-guided design (Miethke et al., 2021; Schneider, 2021). Nevertheless, bacterial infections and its dynamics continue to pose major public health challenges worldwide. In specific context, the antimicrobial resistance (AMR), treatment failure, and recurrent infections.

A major health concern, therefore, is the growing prevalence of AMR as antimicrobial therapy is increasingly compromised. Hence, resistant pathogens are associated with prolonged illness, increased healthcare expenditure, reduced therapeutic options, and elevated mortality rates (Tacconelli *et al.*, 2017). Also, resistance alone does not fully explain the complexity of treatment outcomes. Increasing evidence indicates that bacterial persistence, tolerance, phenotypic heterogeneity, and biofilm formation can contribute to prolonged infection and treatment failure (Penesyan *et al.*, 2015; Gajdacs, 2019). These mechanisms enable subpopulations of bacteria to survive and may lead to delayed clearance, persistent colonisation, or recurrent infection.

Traditional approaches commonly used rely on microbiological susceptibility testing, minimum inhibitory concentration measurements, and binary clinical outcomes (Salam *et al.*, 2023). While these methods provide valuable information, they often fail to capture the temporal dynamics of bacterial responses during treatment. Consequently, analyses based solely on baseline and endpoint assessments may overlook important changes occurring throughout treatment and follow-up. Methods of Longitudinal statistical (LS) investigates changes in bacterial status over time by accounting for repeated observations collected from the same patient (Alanin *et al.*, 2015). Generalised Estimating Equations (GEE) (Zhou *et al.*, 2019) are useful for estimating population-averaged effects of treatment and patient characteristics on bacterial persistence and within-subject correlation. Complementary to LS, survival analysis evaluates treatment response by transforming bacterial clearance into a time-to-event outcome. Both Kaplan-Meier Estimate (KME) and Cox Proportional Hazards (CPH) regression (Ahmad *et al.*, 2024) enable quantification of clearance probabilities, median time-to-clearance, and identification of factors influencing bacterial eradication. Dynamics of antimicrobial response that are not obtainable from conventional cross-sectional analyses are what these models offer.

Studies in Machine Learning (ML) have further expanded opportunities for modelling complex task, including clinical outcomes (Adham *et al.*, 2017; Tao *et al.*, 2023). Many of the approaches have shown promise for risk stratification and outcome prediction in a variety of biomedical applications. Nevertheless, their comparative utility relative to established statistical survival models remains insufficient. Also, there remains limited understanding of how bacterial states evolve throughout treatment and how these transitions influence subsequent clinical outcomes. In particular for settings characterised by limited longitudinal clinical data.

This study, therefore, proposes an integrated antimicrobial therapy response and bacterial dynamics using hybrid survival and ML approaches. The contribution of study include:

- i. characterising temporal patterns of bacterial Clearance, Persistence, and Recurrence (CPR) through patient-state transition analysis;
- ii. evaluating population-averaged treatment effects using GEE, models time-to-bacterial clearance using KME-CPH methods, and;
- iii. benchmarking classical survival models against Random Survival Forests (RSF) and Gradient Boosted Survival (GBS) algorithms.

2. RELATED WORKS

Studies on antimicrobial therapy has focused on improving treatment effectiveness through the discovery of antibacterial agents and the optimisation of therapeutic regimens (da Cunha *et al.*, 2019; Schneider, 2021). Infusion of AI (Egwuche *et al.*, 2026), systems biology, and precision medicine into antimicrobial research is accelerating drug discovery and improve treatment selection (Brussow, 2024; Miethke *et al.*, 2021; Rugarabamu & Mwanyika, 2025). Despite, treatment success remains constrained by the complex biological responses of bacterial populations during and after antimicrobial exposure.

A major challenge in antimicrobial therapy is the persistence of bacterial populations despite treatment.

Phenotypic heterogeneity within bacterial populations enables subsets of cells to survive antimicrobial exposure without acquiring heritable resistance mechanisms (Huang *et al.*, 2025). Penesyan *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that biofilm-associated bacterial communities exhibit enhanced tolerance to antimicrobial agents and can serve as reservoirs for persistent infection. Similarly, Gajdács (2019) highlighted the importance of bacterial persisters and dormant cells in sustaining infections and contributing to relapse following apparently successful treatment. These findings suggest that antimicrobial response is governed by dynamic bacterial survival strategies that extend beyond conventional resistance mechanisms.

Mathematical and mechanistic models were further employed to characterise bacterial persistence and treatment response. Modelling investigations involving Methicillin-Resistant-Staphylococcus Aureus (MRSA), and other clinically important pathogens have shown that bacterial populations often exhibit life-threatening behaviour. Mikkaichi *et al.* (2019) integrated ensemble mathematical modelling with ML to investigate persistent MRSA bacteremia. Results suggested that host-mediated clearance mechanisms play a more influential role in infection resolution than bacterial switching rates alone. The study focuses on mechanistic processes rather than patient-level longitudinal treatment outcomes.

Furthermore, recurrence has been associated with incomplete bacterial eradication, biofilm survival, persistent reservoirs, and host-related risk factors. Li *et al.* (2025) developed ML models for predicting recurrent MRSA bacteremia using clinical and laboratory data to identify recurrence risk. Likewise, Vodstrcil *et al.* (2021) reported that recurrent bacterial vaginosis is strongly associated with microbial persistence and failure of microbiome restoration following treatment. Findings indicate that treatment outcomes through endpoint assessments are not enough, rather an account that allow for the temporal evolution of bacterial states during follow-up. In addition, the increasing availability of repeated clinical was widely assessed using GEE in biomedical research to estimate population-averaged effects. KME and CPH regression have become standard tools for investigating clinically meaningful outcomes (Ahmad *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, in antimicrobial research, ML has been applied to recurrence prediction, biomarker identification, resistance surveillance, and treatment outcome forecasting (Li *et al.*, 2025; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Aside predictive analytics, hybrid frameworks combining mechanistic models and ML have also emerged (Leber *et al.*, 2017).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Transition-State Concept

Transition-state, shown in Figure 1 represents patient bacterial status as a sequence of clinically meaningful states observed throughout follow-up. Following antibiotic administration, patients initially occupy the bacterial Positive state as detectable bacterial presence. Over time, individuals may transition to a Cleared state, representing successful bacterial eradication, or enter a Persistent Positive state, reflecting continued bacterial detection despite ongoing treatment. Persistence is considered an intermediate state associated with delayed response, potential antimicrobial tolerance, or incomplete bacterial elimination.

Patients who achieve clearance may remain bacteria-free throughout follow-up or subsequently transition to a Recurrent Positive state, indicating reappearance of detectable bacteria after an initial period of clearance. Recurrent positivity may arise from relapse of the original infection, survival of residual bacterial populations, reinfection, or incomplete eradication of persister cells.

3.2 Dataset Description

This study utilised the bacterial dataset obtained from the MedDataSets package developed by Rossi (2024). The dataset contains longitudinal observations collected from a clinical trial investigating the presence of bacteria in patients receiving different antimicrobial treatments. A total of 220 observations from 50 patients were recorded across multiple follow-up visits. It further includes capturing bacterial status, treatment assignment, antibiotic susceptibility, baseline bacterial load, and treatment duration. The

outcome variable represents the presence or absence of bacteria during follow-up. The variables included in the dataset and description is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1. Transition-state model of the antimicrobial study

Table 1. Description of the bacterial dataset

Variable	Type	Description
y	Factor	Presence (1) or absence (0) of bacteria at follow-up
ap	Factor	Antibiotic susceptibility test result (Yes/No)
hilo	Factor	Baseline bacterial load categorized as High or Low
week	Integer	Follow-up week of treatment assessment
ID	Factor	Unique patient identifier (50 patients)
trt	Factor	Treatment group assignment (placebo, drug, drug+)

3.3 Methods

The proposed model a stochastic longitudinal state-transition and survival modelling framework. The longitudinal population average model, GEE is expressed as:

$$\text{logit}(P(Y_{it} = 1))\beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Treatment} + \beta_2 \text{Week} + \beta_3 \text{Baseline Load} + \beta_4 (\text{Treatment} \times \text{Week}) \quad (1)$$

where Y_{it} , i , and t denote bacterial positivity status, patient, and follow-up time, respectively. The state-transition model is then defined as:

$$\text{Positive} \rightarrow \text{Persistence} \rightarrow \text{Recurrent} \quad (2)$$

or

$$\text{Positive} \rightarrow \text{Persistence} \quad (3)$$

The transition matrix is, therefore, written as:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} P_{PP} & P_{PC} & P_{PR} \\ P_{CP} & P_{CC} & P_{CR} \\ P_{RP} & P_{RC} & P_{RR} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $p_{ij} = P(S_{t+1} = j | S_t = i)$, a discrete-time Markov transition framework.

The bacterial persistence is transformed into a survival process as time-to-clearance event expressed as:

$$S(t) = P(T > t) \quad (4)$$

where T represent time until bacterial clearance.

Furthermore, the KME estimates and CPH for the model is defined as:

$$\hat{S}(t) = \prod_{t_i \leq t} \left(1 - \frac{d_i}{n_i}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$h(t|X) = h_0(t) \exp(\beta X) \quad (6)$$

quantifying hazard of clearance or rate of persistence resolution

Both RSF and GBS are defined as follows:

$$\hat{S}(t|X) \quad (7)$$

achieved through ensemble survival trees.

$$f(X) = \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_m h_m(X) \quad (8)$$

where each h_m is a survival tree.

A generalised Persistence-Clearance transition model is, therefore, formulated as:

$$P_t = P_0 e^{-\lambda t} \quad (9)$$

where P_t denotes probability of remaining bacterial positive at time t and λ , the clearance rate. The P_t is directly estimable from KME-CPH results. For recurrence:

$$R(t) = 1 - e^{-\gamma t} \quad (10)$$

where $R(t)$ and γ denote recurrence probability and recurrence intensity. The combined approach is expressed as:

$$B(t) = P_0 e^{-\lambda t} + \theta(1 - e^{-\gamma t}) \quad (11)$$

where θ is the recurrence proportion.

3.4 Experimental Setup

The experiment investigates bacterial CPR following antimicrobial therapy. To account for within-patient correlation arising from repeated observations, both Exchangeable as “model 1” and First-Order Autoregressive (AR1) as “model 2” working correlation structures were examined. Model selection was based on the Quasi-likelihood under the Independence Model Criterion (QIC), with the best-performing correlation structure adopted for subsequent inference. Bacterial clearance was defined as the first observed transition from bacterial positivity to bacterial negativity and was subsequently analysed using KME estimation and CPH. Model performance was assessed through internal validation using 3-fold cross-validation, whereby the dataset was partitioned into three approximately equal subsets. During each iteration, two subsets were used for model training and one subset was reserved for testing. This ensures all observations participated in both training and validation. Predictive performance was quantified using Harrell’s concordance index (C-index), while bootstrap-based optimism correction and calibration analyses were employed to evaluate model robustness and generalizability. All analyses were conducted using the R statistical computing environment and Rstudio. Specialized R packages used include ggplot2, geepack, survival, survminer, randomForestSRC, gbm, caret, and related analytical libraries.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The study included 50 participants distributed across three treatment groups and characterized according to antibiotic susceptibility status and baseline bacterial load, as presented in Table 2. The placebo group consisted entirely of antibiotic-resistant cases, while the active treatment groups comprised antibiotic-

susceptible patients with either low or high baseline bacterial burden.

Table 2. Baseline Characteristics of Participants

trt	ap	hilo	n
placebo	Resistant	Low	8
placebo	Resistant	High	13
drug	Susceptible	Low	14
drug+	Susceptible	High	15

The prevalence-time analysis demonstrated a progressive reduction in bacterial positivity throughout follow-up, decreasing from approximately 90% at baseline to about 57% by Week 11 (Figure 2). This decline suggests that bacterial clearance occurred in a substantial proportion of patients during treatment and follow-up. However, the persistence of bacterial positivity in more than half of the cohort at the final visit indicates that complete eradication was not universally achieved. Treatment-specific prevalence trajectories (Figure 3) revealed more pronounced reductions in bacterial positivity among the active treatment groups than in the placebo group. It suggests improved bacterial clearance among treated patients. Nevertheless, bacterial positivity remained evident across all groups at the end of follow-up, indicating continued persistence or recurrence in some individuals.

Moreover, longitudinal bacterial status in Table 3 showed a gradual increase in bacterial-negative observations from 5 cases at baseline to 12 cases by Week 11. It was accompanied by a corresponding decline in bacterial-positive observations from 45 to 32 cases. These findings provide evidence of bacterial clearance over time but also indicate substantial residual positivity throughout follow-up.

Figure 2. Prevalence to Time curve

Figure 3. Prevalence to Treatment curve

Meanwhile, the transition-state analysis (Figure 4) revealed considerable heterogeneity in treatment response. Persistent positivity represented the dominant trajectory, accounting for 52% of participants, while only 20% achieved sustained bacterial clearance. Recurrent positivity occurred in 14% of patients, indicating reappearance of bacteria after an initial clearance event. Baseline-negative and mixed/irregular patterns accounted for 10% and 4% of participants, respectively. The dynamic movement of patients between bacterial states over successive visits further highlight that treatment response is not a simple binary outcome (Figure 5). It is rather a complex process involving CPR.

Furthermore, GEE models produced highly consistent results under both “model 1” and “model 2” correlation structures, suggesting robustness of the longitudinal findings, as presented in Table 4. Neither

treatment group demonstrated a statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) reduction in bacterial positivity relative to placebo treatment effect, Similarly, baseline bacterial load was not significantly associated with clearance probability (HR = 0.84, 95% CI: 0.14–5.02, $p = 0.847$) in Tables 5 and 6. However, the week coefficient was negative in both models and approached statistical significance, which indicates a gradual decline in bacterial positivity as treatment progressed.

Table 3. Longitudinal Bacterial Status by Follow-Up Week and Treatment

<i>week</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>trt</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>n</i>
0	<i>n</i>	5	<i>placebo</i>	<i>n</i>	12
0	<i>y</i>	45	<i>placebo</i>	<i>y</i>	84
2	<i>n</i>	4	<i>drug</i>	<i>n</i>	18
2	<i>y</i>	40	<i>drug</i>	<i>y</i>	44
4	<i>n</i>	11	<i>drug+</i>	<i>n</i>	13
4	<i>y</i>	31	<i>drug+</i>	<i>y</i>	49
6	<i>n</i>	11			
6	<i>y</i>	29			
11	<i>n</i>	12			
11	<i>y</i>	32			

Figure 4. Transition classes

Although treatment effects were not statistically significant, the direction of the estimated odds ratios suggests a tendency toward reduced bacterial positivity among patients receiving active therapy. The absence of statistical significance is likely attributable to the limited sample size and relatively small number of clearance events. Importantly, the consistency between Exchangeable and AR1 structures strengthens confidence in the observed temporal trend toward bacterial reduction during follow-up.

KME analysis demonstrated progressive bacterial clearance throughout the observation period, as presented in Table 5. The probability of remaining bacteria-positive declined from 91.1% at Week 2 to 56.8% by Week 11, which indicate approximately 43% of participants achieved bacterial clearance during follow-up. Confidence intervals widened over time, reflecting increasing uncertainty as the number of

patients at risk decreased (Table 6).

Figure 5. Follow-up visit to patient Sankey Plot

The treatment-specific KME-curves suggested improved clearance among patients receiving active antimicrobial therapy compared with placebo. Median clearance time was estimated at 6 weeks for the drug group and 4 weeks for the drug+ group. Whereas the placebo group did not achieve sufficient clearance events to estimate a median time-to-clearance (Figure 6). The lack of statistical significance, together with the wide confidence intervals, suggests limited statistical power rather than absence of biological effect (Figures 6 and 7). The survival analyses indicate a favourable trend toward faster bacterial clearance under active therapy.

Table 4. GEE Population-Averaged Longitudinal result

Term	Estimate	std.error	statistic	p.value	Model	Odds_Ratio	Lower_95CI	Upper_95CI
(Intercept)	2.0359	0.6314	10.3966	0.0013	1	7.659	2.222	26.4034
trtdrug	-0.6542	0.7617	0.7377	0.3904	1	0.52	0.117	2.3134
trtdrug+	-0.4101	0.812	0.2551	0.6135	1	0.664	0.135	3.2586
week	-0.0884	0.0482	3.3626	0.0667	1	0.915	0.833	1.0061
hiloHigh	0.5765	0.8171	0.4979	0.4804	1	1.78	0.359	8.8286
trtdrug:week	-0.0166	0.0815	0.0413	0.839	1	0.984	0.838	1.1539
trtdrug+:week	-0.0842	0.0951	0.7838	0.376	1	0.919	0.763	1.1076
(Intercept)	2.0288	0.6419	9.9899	0.0016	2	7.605	2.161	26.7611
trtdrug	-0.6783	0.7685	0.779	0.3775	2	0.508	0.113	2.2886
trtdrug+	-0.4743	0.803	0.3489	0.5548	2	0.622	0.129	3.0031
week	-0.0903	0.0502	3.2348	0.0721	2	0.914	0.828	1.0081
hiloHigh	0.596	0.824	0.5232	0.4695	2	1.815	0.361	9.1262
trtdrug:week	-0.0032	0.0808	0.0016	0.968	2	0.997	0.851	1.1679
trtdrug+:week	-0.0647	0.097	0.4445	0.505	2	0.937	0.775	1.1336

Table 5. KME Summary Table

Time (Weeks)	At Risk	Events	Survival Probability	95% CI
2	45	4	0.911	0.832–0.998
4	41	6	0.778	0.665–0.909

6	34	7	0.618	0.500–0.779
11	25	2	0.568	0.439–0.736

Table 6. KME and CPH Analysis of Bacterial Clearance

Variable	Category	Patients (n)	Events (n)	Median Clearance Time (Weeks)	Hazard Ratio (HR)	95% CI	p-value
Treatment	Placebo	19	5	Not Reached	Reference	–	–
	Drug	12	6	6	2.12	0.43–10.50	0.359
	Drug+	14	8	4	2.63	0.69–9.93	0.155
Baseline Load	Low	19	8	6	Reference	–	–
	High	26	11	6	0.84	0.14–5.02	0.847

Figure 6. KME per Treatment Clearance Curves

Figure 7. KME per week Clearance Curves

Additionally, comparison of survival prediction models is presented in Table 7. It was observed that the CPH model achieved the highest discrimination performance with a C-index of 0.587, outperforming both RSF of 0.500) and GBS of 0.393. These results indicate that the conventional Cox model provided the most reliable predictions for bacterial clearance in the present dataset. The comparatively weaker performance of the ML models likely reflects the small sample size and limited predictor set, conditions under which highly flexible algorithms may struggle to identify stable predictive patterns. Model diagnostics and validation analyses supported the adequacy of the Cox model. The proportional hazards diagnostic plot showed no evidence of severe violation of model assumptions (Figure 8).

Moreover, CHP suggests active antimicrobial therapy may accelerate bacterial clearance compared with placebo, as shown in Figure 9. Patients receiving the drug and drug+ treatments exhibited approximately 2.1-fold (HR = 2.12, 95% CI: 0.43–10.50) and 2.6-fold (HR = 2.63, 95% CI: 0.69–9.93) higher clearance rates, respectively. While these effects were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), the positive direction and magnitude of the hazard ratios indicate a potentially meaningful treatment benefit. In contrast, baseline bacterial load showed little influence on clearance dynamics (HR = 0.84, 95% CI: 0.14–5.02, $p = 0.80$). Observation in Figure 9 further reveals a consistent trend of improved bacterial clearance among treated patients, particularly in the drug+ group. The wide confidence intervals highlight the uncertainty arising from the small sample size and limited number of clearance events.

Also, bootstrap validation demonstrated relatively modest optimism, indicating limited overfitting (Figure 10). Furthermore, the calibration plot showed reasonable agreement between predicted and observed event probabilities across risk strata, suggesting acceptable predictive calibration (Figure 11). Collectively, these findings indicate that although machine learning approaches offer theoretical advantages for capturing nonlinear relationships, traditional survival modelling provided superior predictive performance and

interpretability for this relatively small longitudinal antimicrobial dataset.

Table 7. ML Comparative result

<i>Model</i>	<i>C_Index</i>
<i>CEPH</i>	0.58702
<i>RSF</i>	0.5000
<i>GBS</i>	0.39326

Figure 8. CPH Diagnostics

Variable	N	Hazard ratio	p	
trt	placebo	19	Reference	
	drug	12	2.12 (0.43, 10.50)	0.4
	drug+	14	2.63 (0.69, 9.93)	0.2
hilo	Low	19	Reference	
	High	26	0.84 (0.14, 5.02)	0.8

Figure 9. Cox Forest plot

Figure 10. Bootstrap optimism

Figure 11. Calibration plot

4.2 Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate that bacterial response to antimicrobial therapy is a dynamic process characterized by CPR rather than a simple binary treatment outcome. Longitudinal prevalence analysis revealed a gradual reduction in bacterial positivity throughout follow-up. Transition-state analysis identified persistent positivity as the dominant response pattern. More than half of the patients remained persistently positive despite treatment, whereas only a minority achieved sustained clearance. These observations support previous reports that treatment failure attributed to AMR, bacterial persistence, phenotypic heterogeneity, and survival mechanisms (Penesyán *et al.*, 2015; Gajdács, 2019; Huang *et al.*,

2025). Those factors that allow bacterial populations to withstand antimicrobial exposure without acquiring genetic resistance. The presence of recurrent positivity reinforces the notion that bacterial eradication and long-term infection control involve complex biological processes.

The GEE analysis indicated a consistent decline in bacterial positivity over time, although treatment effects did not reach statistical significance. Nevertheless, the negative temporal trend observed across both Exchangeable and AR1 correlation structures suggests that bacterial burden decreased progressively during follow-up. This observation is consistent with studies reporting biphasic bacterial killing patterns, in which rapid initial bacterial reduction is followed by slower elimination of persistent subpopulations (Mikkaichi *et al.*, 2019). The findings across alternative correlation structures strengthens confidence in the observed temporal dynamics. It further highlights the value of longitudinal modelling for capturing changes in bacterial status that may be overlooked by conventional endpoint-based analyses.

In addition, the survival analyses provided further insight into bacterial clearance dynamics. KME estimates showed a progressive decline in the probability of remaining bacteria-positive. Whereas CPH modelling suggested that patients receiving active antimicrobial therapy experienced approximately 2- to 3-fold higher clearance rates than those receiving placebo. These effects were observed not statistically significant; however, the direction and magnitude of the hazard ratios indicate a potentially meaningful therapeutic benefit. Similar observations have been reported in studies of persistent bacterial infections, where antimicrobial treatment contributes to improved clearance; but may not completely eliminate persister populations responsible for prolonged infection and recurrence (Mikkaichi *et al.*, 2019; Vodstreil *et al.*, 2021). The wide confidence intervals observed in the present study likely reflect the relatively small sample size and limited number of clearance events rather than the absence of a biological treatment effect. The CPH model outperformed both RSF and GBS models in terms of discrimination performance. This finding suggests that, for relatively small clinical datasets with limited predictors, classical survival models may provide greater stability, interpretability performance than more complex ML algorithms. While recent studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of ML for predicting recurrence and treatment outcomes (Li *et al.*, 2025; Wang *et al.*, 2024), the present results indicate that model complexity alone does not guarantee improved predictive performance. Instead, the integration of LS, transition-state modelling, survival analysis, and ML could provide for understanding antimicrobial therapy response and bacterial dynamics.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study has opened up a debate that bacterial infections contribute to substantial burden in global health outcomes. Findings has revealed that bacterial response is a dynamic process characterised by multiple transition pathways rather than a simple cured-versus-not-cured outcome. Persistence emerged as the dominant bacterial trajectory, while active antimicrobial therapies demonstrated a tendency toward faster bacterial clearance compared with placebo. Survival analysis further showed that patients receiving active treatment experienced higher clearance rates, although the observed effects did not achieve statistical significance.

In addition, ML survival models were capable of capturing complex relationships within the data. However, the CPH model achieved superior predictive performance and calibration. Finding suggests that for relatively small longitudinal clinical datasets, interpretable statistical survival models may provide more stable and reliable predictions than highly ML algorithms. Furthermore, the transition-state offered clinically meaningful insights into the evolution of bacterial status over time (monitoring persistence, recurrence, and clearance).

Future research should validate the proposed framework using larger and more diverse antimicrobial datasets containing richer clinical, microbiological, pharmacological, and host-related variables. Additional

studies may incorporate advanced survival ML techniques such as DeepSurv, XGBoost Survival, and dynamic Bayesian models to better characterise transitions between bacterial states. Furthermore, integrating genomic and microbiome data may improve the prediction of persistence and recurrence with deeper insights into the biological mechanisms underlying treatment response.

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